

Sample 27a

Greyscale Image

PARC Phases

	area %
{Pb-rich}	0.0014
{Si}	63.4
{Al, Si}	13.7
{Ca}	7.1
{Fe}	4.0
{Si, Ca HIP}	2.5
{Si, Ca LoP}	1.7
{Si, Fe}	0.9
{Al, Si, Ca}	0.8
{Al, Si, K}	0.6
{Al}	0.6
{Al, Ca}	0.5
{Na, Al, Si}	0.5
{Zn-LA1}	0.4
{Mg, Si}	0.4
{Si, K}	0.3
{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
{Ti}	0.2
{Na, Si}	0.2
{Mg, Ca}	0.2
{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.2
{P}	0.2
{S, Ca}	0.2
{Si, Fe}	0.1
{P, Ca}	0.1
{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.1
{S}	0.1
{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
{Ca, Fe}	0.1
{Si, P}	0.1
{Mg}	0.0
{S, Ba-LA1}	0.0
{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
{Al, Si, S}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.9
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	1.3
BOF converter slag slopping	0.6
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.3
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.1
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.4
Fe-metal rich	0.1
Coal and cokes or soil	60.8
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	1.4
Carbon rich - other	6.5
Cement or BOF converter	0.2
Cement	0.0
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	1.2
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	22.2
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.0
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.9
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	2.2
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.1
Site - flux / slag	0.0
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.4
Urban + site - scrap	0.1
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	60.8
Site - carbon-rich other	1.4
Site - carbon-rich other, + natural + urban	6.5
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.2
Urban	1.2
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	22.2
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.0
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 27b

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0046
	{Si}	67.3
	{Al, Si}	12.3
	{Ca}	4.5
	{Fe}	3.3
	{S}	2.3
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.8
	{Al, Si, K}	1.5
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.0
	{Na, Al, Si}	1.0
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Al}	0.8
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.4
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Na, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca}	0.2
	{Ca, Fe}	0.2
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
	{S, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, Ca, Fe}	0.0
	{Si, P}	0.0
	{Mg, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{P}	0.0
	{Al, Si, S}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

141 μm

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.2
Pellet	0.0
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.1
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.1
BOF converter slag	0.0
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	0.3
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.4
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	56.1
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.9
Carbon rich - other	7.4
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.5
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.4
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	28.3
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	5.3
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.3
Site - ore / hot metal	0.1
Site - slag	0.0
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	0.3
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.4
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	56.1
Site - carbon-rich other	0.9
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	7.4
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	0.9
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	28.3
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	5.3
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/o partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Sample 27c

Greyscale Image

141 μm

PARC Phases

		area %
	{Pb-rich}	0.0168
	{Si}	61.3
	{Al, Si}	11.6
	{S}	8.9
	{Ca}	6.3
	{Fe}	3.1
	{Si, Ca HiP}	1.9
	{Si, Ca LoP}	1.2
	{Si, Fe}	0.9
	{Al, Si, K}	0.7
	{Na, Al, Si}	0.6
	{Al, Si, Ca}	0.6
	{Si, K}	0.3
	{Al}	0.3
	{Mg, Si}	0.3
	{Mg, Al, Si}	0.2
	{Na, Si}	0.2
	{Mg, Ca}	0.2
	{Ti}	0.1
	{Al, Ca}	0.1
	{Mg, Si, Ca}	0.1
	{P, Ca}	0.1
	{Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Mn}	0.1
	{S, Ca}	0.1
	{Ca, Fe}	0.1
	{Zn-LA1}	0.1
	{Si, S, Ca}	0.1
	{P}	0.1
	{Al, Si, Fe}	0.1
	{Si, P, Ca}	0.0
	{Mg, Al, Si, Ca}	0.0
	{Si, P}	0.0
	{S, Fe}	0.0
	{Mg}	0.0

area % is excl. empty spectra

Source materials (detailed)

	area %
Sinter	0.0
Pellet	0.2
Ore preparation undifferentiated	0.2
Ore preparation Mn-rich	0.0
Ore / hot metal	0.0
BOF converter slag	0.4
BOF converter slag slopping	0.0
Slag BOF converter or desulph	0.0
Desulph slag	0.0
Ca-aluminate slag	0.0
Blast furnace slag	0.0
Dolomite residue - iron- and steelmaking	0.0
Olivine flux	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - diverse	0.0
Ca-carbonate or hydroxide - iron- and steelmaking	1.1
Dolomite residue or refractory MgO	0.0
MgO with spinel - refractory	0.0
Tundish gunning mass	0.0
Alumina	0.0
Fe-FeOx with Zn-compounds	0.0
Rich in Zn-compounds	0.0
Fe-metal rich	0.0
Coal and cokes or soil	53.6
Carbon rich with steelmaking phases	0.6
Carbon rich - other	22.2
Cement or BOF converter	0.0
Cement	0.8
Gypsum or anhydrite	0.0
Ti-rich paint	0.0
Ba-sulphate bearing	0.0
Na-Ca-silicate rich	0.0
Al-corrosion/salts	0.0
Salt or salt layer	0.0
Qz-clay-fsp-mica GT 60 pct	16.4
Qz-clay-fsp-mica 30-60 pct	4.4
Misc silicates including natural	0.0
Possible ore gangue silicate	0.0
Apatite	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate dominated	0.0
Ca-Al-silicate with Ca-silicate	0.0
Na-sulphate rich	0.0
Pb-rich GT 40 pct	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct Na-rich chloride	0.0
Unassigned with GT 30 pct other chloride	0.0
Unassigned with detected Pb-rich	0.0
Unassigned other	0.0

141 μm

Source categories

	area %
Site - ore	0.4
Site - ore / hot metal	0.0
Site - slag	0.4
Site - slag, urban	0.0
Site - flux	0.0
Site - flux / slag, + natural	0.0
Site - flux / slag	1.1
Site - flux / refractory	0.0
Site - refractory	0.0
Site - scrap	0.0
Urban + site - scrap	0.0
Site - coal & cokes; + natural + urban	53.6
Site - carbon-rich other	0.6
Site - carbon-rich other; + natural + urban	22.2
Urban, rarely site - slag	0.0
Urban	0.8
Natural salt - immediate	0.0
Natural mineral background	16.4
Natural mineral background mixed site / urban	4.4
Natural source - immediate + via site	0.0
Unknown	0.0
Pb-rich various	0.0
Unassigned (w/wo partial chloride cover)	0.0

All Populations

Populations containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels

Phases in grains containing 1 or more Pb pixels